

PHONETIC PHENOMENA IN UZBEK LINGUISTICS

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Annotation: In this article, we have briefly touched on the most common and widely used phonetic phenomena in our speech and in the Uzbek literary language. We unknowingly use a variety of phonetic phenomena in our speech to make it easier to pronounce. These phonetic phenomena occur as a result of a single sound.

Keywords: phonetics, sound, articulation, phonology, word, syllable, sound drop, sound exchange, morphology.

Each word in our speech has its own phonetic tone. Although a separate sound does not mean anything, it does form the outside of meaningful language units, making them audible. The most important language units in spoken language are words and sounds. Other events serve to realize the meaning of the word. When a word has a meaning, sounds convey it to the listener. It is the social control of the voice that conveys the meaning to the listener in the form of words. There are aspects of sound formation, hearing, and meaning. The physiological (articulatory) and acoustic (auditory) features of sound are important only to the linguist. The difference in

meaning is important for the speakers, who use it unconsciously. Speech sound is one of the first language units. The first biological sounds that emerged through human language evolved into social sounds as human thought evolved. Phonetic theories of the origin of languages are not in vain. Of course, the fact that the problem is posed in the form of words, not languages, shows that all the existing theories are correct.¹

Phonetics (Greek *phonetike*, *phonetikos* --- sound) linguist. 1. The branch of linguistics that studies the methods of formation, acoustic properties and composition of speech sounds². Phonetics is the lowest level of linguistics and the field of linguistics that studies this level. Phonetics (*gr.phonetikos* - sound, sound-specific), unlike other areas of linguistics, examines not only the functional side of the source of learning, but also the pronunciation apparatus that produces speech sounds, as well as their acoustic properties and perceptions by language owners. In phonetics, the connection between linguistics and other disciplines, such as literature, physiology, physics, and psychology, becomes even clearer. In contrast to these disciplines, phonetics views sounds as an element of the language system that gives words, affixes, and sentences a material appearance. Phonetics also studies the changes and exchanges of sounds in speech, as well as stress and its types³.

The study of phonetics is important in mastering the rules of spelling, correct pronunciation (*orthoepy*), in distinguishing between literary and dialectal pronunciation, in the diagnosis and elimination of speech defects in speech therapy and deaf pedagogy. Advances in phonetics play an important role in testing and enhancing communication, as well as in the automatic detection of speech. Phonetics is primarily divided into general, specific, and comparative phonetics. General

¹ **Hozirgi o'zbek tili (kirish, fonetik sath, liksik-semantik sath)** darslik. Baxtiyor Mengliyev – Toshkent: «Tafakkur bo'stoni», 2018. – 82 b.

² O'zbek tilining izohli lug'ati ---- T.: “ O'zbekiston milliy ensiklopediyasi” davlat ilmiy nashriyoti. 4-jild. 356-bet

³ Abduazizov A.A. O'zbek tilining fonologiyasi va morfonologiyasi. –T.:O'qituvchi, 1992.

features of the formation of speech sounds in the human pronunciation apparatus from the product (for example, the difference of lips, tongue, throat consonants instead of the formation of consonants, explosive according to the formation, sirg. (determination of the properties of receiving, explosive-sliding sounds, etc.), the general acoustic properties of sounds are studied. Partially based on articulatory and partly on caustic signs, it also deals with the internal parts of speech sounds that are universal, distinguishing features.

Phonetic changes in speech.

The result is a chain of sounds. As a result of the effort to ease pronunciation, various phonetic changes occur in the chain of sounds during speech. For example, if we add the suffix -gach to the base of a white word, the deep tongue at the end of the base will be followed by the back g of the tongue, making it difficult for the deep tongue to suddenly switch from the back to the back of the tongue. Pronunciation discomfort occurs. The result is a chain of sounds. As a result of the effort to ease pronunciation, various phonetic changes occur in the chain of sounds during speech. For example, if we add the suffix -gach to the base of a white word, the deep tongue at the end of the base will be followed by the back g of the tongue, making it difficult for the deep tongue to suddenly switch from the back to the back of the tongue. Pronunciation discomfort occurs. To eliminate this inconvenience, the second sound is also converted into a deep tongue back sound to achieve comfort. Compare: sown, sown, sown. The sounds in a word can change without interfering with each other. The position of the sound in the word structure (in what order); the beginning or end of a word, with or without an accent, plays an important role. For example, the consonant "b" at the end of the words etiquette, answer, mask, school is pronounced as a consonant "p" in the pronunciation; the consonant "v" at the end of Russian-international words such as negative, normative-positive, operative in the form of a consonant "f" without a vowel; the vowel "o" in the unstressed syllable of Russian-international words such as volleyball, olympiad is pronounced as "a": volleyball, olympiad. This can be caused by a tendency to be concise in speech, a lack of emphasis in the syllable, a hurried pronunciation, or difficulty pronouncing words

in other languages. Phonetic phenomena or fusion phenomena are changes in speech that occur as a result of the interaction of successive sounds due to the movement to achieve ease of pronunciation. Phonetic phenomena apply to both vowels and consonants.

Assimilation --- the adaptation of one sound to a side sound or the similarity of two different sounds. There are two types of assimilation. Progressive assimilation is when the next sound changes under the influence of the previous sound. When the previous sound changes under the influence of the next sound, it is called regressive assimilation.

Pronunciation only: *ot + di = otti, ket + di = ketti, tuz + siz = tussiz, yoz + sin = yossin, xat + ni = xatti, ish + ga = ishka, taqsim = taxsim, shanba = shamba, tanbur = tambur.*

Reflected in both pronunciation and writing: *son+a=sana, ong+la=angla, ot+a=ata, yosh+a=yasha, chiq+gan=chiqqan, qishloq+ga=qishloqqa, tik+gan=tikkan, non+voy=novvoy, bir+ta=bitta, tilak+ga=tilakka, tuzuk+gina=tuzukkina.*

Dissimilation --- when two identical or partially similar sounds interact. This phenomenon can be called the opposite of assimilation. There are two types of dissimilation. When the next sound changes under the influence of the previous sound, it is called progressive dissimilation. When the previous sound changes under the influence of the next sound, it is called regressive dissimilation.

Pronunciation only: *zarur=zaril, maqta=maxta, uch+ta=ushta, koridor=kolidor, zarar=zaral, devor=devol, ittifoq=intifoq.*

Reflected in both pronunciation and writing: *qishloq+i=qishlog'i, qishloq+ing=qishlog'ing, tala+n=talon, qara+l=qarol, tara+q=taroq, birorta=bironta.*

Metathesis --- the alternation of adjacent sounds. This phenomenon is more common in live speech, especially in dialects, and less common in literary language: *tuproq=turpoq, to'g'ramoq=to'rg'amoq, daryo=dayro, afv=avf, ahvol=avhol, supra=surpa.*

Phonetic events include the addition, subtraction, and amplification of sounds.

VOICE INCREASE EVENTS		
basis + word maker	Increased volume as a result of word formation	achi+q=achchiq, isi+q=issiq, sisi+q=sassiq, his+iy=hissiy, tib+iy=tibbiy, jiz+a=jizza, shart+a=shartta, taq+q=taqqa, shar+os=sharros, var+ak=varrak, g'ur+ak=g'urrak...
basis + possession attachments	Some words have an increase in volume as a result of the addition of possessive pronouns I and II	mavzu+im=mavzuyim, obro'+im=obro'yim, mavqe+ing=mavqeying, baho+ing=bahoying, xudo+im=xudoyim, avzo+ing=avzoying, parvo+ing=parvoying...
Show diamond + ownership suffix	That's the decent thing to do, and it should end there	bu+im=bunim, u+ing=uning, o'sha+i+si=o'shanisi, shu+i+si=shunisi..
Show diamond + agreement attachment	It is the increase in sound as a result of the addition of such pronouns as direction, place, and exit.	u+ga=unga, u+da=unda, bu+dan=bundan...
Verb + ratio attachment	I mean, passive and compound adverbs in verbs like eat increase the volume as a result of adding	De+il=deyil, ye+ish+yeyish...

But with the addition of ownership to the word "orzu" there is no sound.

Consonant Augmentation - In this case, consonant sounds are added to the base by adding to the base:

-q, -iq suffix to words such as *achi, isi, sasi*, qot sound is added: *achchiq, issiq, sassiq, qattiq*.

u, bu, shu direction, place-time, exit agreements for show pronouns (-ga, -da, -dan) and -day, -cha f attachments are added – n sound is gained: *unga, bunga, shunga, unda, bundan, shundan, shuncha, bunday*.

VOICES INCREASE IN PRONUNCIATION		
PROTEZA	Increased volume at the beginning of a word	Stol=istol, stul=istul, stakan=istakan..
EPENTEZA	Increased volume in the middle of a word	Trakor=tiraktor, fikr=fikir, uzr=uzur, hukm=hokum, oila=oyila, soat=soxat, sinf=sinif.
EPITEZA	An increase in volume at the end of a word	Tank=tanka, bank=banka, disk=diska

A vowel is a vowel or consonant that is added to a base. For example:

- *past, sust ulug'* The sound is formed when the suffix -ay is added to the words: *pasay, susay.ulg'ay*
- *Yig'i* When the -la verb suffix is added to words such as, the vowel "i" is dropped: *yig'la*;
- *ikki, olti, yetti* Adding a compound suffix (-ov, -ala, -ovlon) to numbers such as: *ikkov, yettalasi, oltov*.
- *men, sen* such as when the suffixes (-ni, -ning) are added to the pronouns: *meni, seni, mening, sening* changes shape.
- *bag'ir, ko'ngil, shahar* Vowels like a, i, u in the second syllable are dropped when the possessive suffix is added to words like: *shahri, ko'ngli, bag'rim, burni* and etc.

- The combination of two words ending in a vowel and beginning with a vowel results in one of the vowels being dropped: *bora oladi-boroladi*
- *Ekan, edi, emish*, Incomplete verbs are sometimes added to the word before them in our speech, and the letter "e" is dropped.: *borarmish, borardi*⁴.

SOUND EVENTS		
basis + possession attachment	Let's have some words sound as a result of the addition of attachments	og'iz+im=og'zim, burun+i=burni, ko'ngil+ing=ko'ngling, bag'ir+i=bag'ri, bo'yin+i=bo'yni, qo'yin+i=qo'yni, singil+im=singlim, qorin+i=qorni, bo'g'iz+ibo'g'zi, o'g'il+i=o'g'li, o'rin+ing=o'ring, egin+im=egnim, yarim+i=yarmi, shahar+i=shahri, zahar+i=zahri...
Basis + word maker	Word-formative affixes to some words sound decreases as a result of	yig'i+la=yig'la, o'yin+a=o'yna, qiyin+a=qiyna, ulug'+ay=ulg'ay, sariq+ay=sarg'ay, qizil+ar=qizar, past+ay=pasay, sust+ay=susay, burur+uq=buyruq, og'iz+aki=og'zaki, ayir+im=ayrim, ingir+a=ingra, ho'ngir+a=ho'ngra, qayir+oq=qayroq, o'rin+a=o'rna,
Verb + ratio attachment	Ayir, qayir adverbs of manner such as passive, personal, and compound sound decreases as a result of	ayir+il=ayril, qayir+qayril, ayir+ish=ayrish

⁴ SH.SHoabdurahmonov va b. Hozirgi o'zbek adabiy tili. I qism. 1980.

Personal pronoun + consonant suffix	Men, sen such as the future tense of pronouns and pronouns sound as a result of the addition of attachments	men+ni=meni, sen+ning=sening..
Number + lexical add-on	Adding suffixes to numbers such as two, seven, or six that make up the meaning of the number	Olti+ov=oltov, ikki+ala=ikkala, yetti+ovlon=yettovlon, olti+mish=oltmish, yetti+mish=yetmish
Elizia	A word that ends in a vowel is a word that begins with a vowel a single vowel drop as a result of	Ayta+oldi=aytoldi, Dili+orom=Dilorom, bora+olmadi=borolmadi, yoza+oladi=yozoladi..
Sandxi event	Sound loss as a result of the contraction of verbs	Ishlar+edi=ishlardi, brogan+emish=borganmish, Borar+ekan=borarkan ⁵ ,

Sound exchange (change) - when one sound is added to the base, one sound is replaced by another:

- *bo 'ya, tara, sana, sayla, tanla* When suffixes -q or -v are added to words such as, the base -a sound is replaced by the -o sound: *bo 'ya+q=bo 'yoq, sana+q=sanoq, tara+q=taroq, sayla+v=saylov, tanla+v=tanlov.*

- *yosh, son, ot* If the suffix -a is added to words such as: *son+a =sana, ot+a=ata, yosh+a=yasha* changes in shape.

- *-ga, -gani, -guncha* When suffixes beginning with the *-g* sound are added to words ending in *-k, q*, the sound changes in the base or suffix: *tekkuncha, terakka, chiqqani, buloqqa, oqquncha*.
- When a possessive suffix is added to a word ending in *-k, -q*, the consonant in the base is replaced by a consonant: *buloq+i-bulog'i, yurak+i-yuragi, tilak+i-tilagi, bilak+i-bilagi*. But *idrok, huquq, mashq, park* if the possessive suffix is added to words such as sound exchange does not occur: *idroki, mashqi, huquqi, parki* and etc. This means that speech sounds can be pronounced differently depending on the letters in the word, as long as the sounds of each language are connected and formed in a certain order according to the rules of each language. In some cases, this spelling is also reflected.

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